

Is the Observable Universe Just a Square Root of the Sporadic Groups?

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Abstract

The direct product of all the 26 sporadic groups is a large group of order 2.333×10^{365} . This group would form a sphere with diameter of $d = 7.638 \times 10^{121}$. The cube root of this group is one of Dirac's large numbers: 6.156×10^{121} , which is the mass of this group. If we take the square root of this group/set the identity of this group to $2\pi \times$ Planck length, we'll get an object with diameter $d = 93.76$ billion ly and weight of 9.63×10^{53} kg. This compares well to current estimates of the diameter of the observable universe of about 92.80 billion ly (error of about 1 %) and mass of 9.288×10^{53} kg (estimated range $9.102 - 9.473 \times 10^{53}$ kg, dark matter + baryonic matter). The relative error for the radius is about 1 % and about 1 % (3.7 %) for mass, since the density of both objects is the same. The observable universe might be related to the direct product of the sporadic groups.

Introduction

There are only 26 sporadic groups that don't fit into any of the infinite families. Their direct product is a large group of an approximate order of 2.333×10^{365} . If we try to write this group with points (each point corresponding to a single member) we'll end up with a sphere with radius of $r = 3.819 \times 10^{121}$ since there is no material light enough not to produce a spherical object with that many points. The cube root of the order is one of Dirac's large numbers: 6.156×10^{121} . A good natural unit will lead to the mass of the object if taken as a cube root, therefore we can think of 6.156×10^{121} as mass of this group. This is remarkably close to the mass of the observable universe if taken in Wesson's mass (about 1.68×10^{-68} kg depending on the value of H_0 used, or about $5 \times 10^{53} - 10^{54}$ kg total).

The smallest possible black hole should have a circumference of $2\pi \times$ Planck length, we'll pick this length unit as an axis/identity with as many members below the length as above. The diameter of our group $r = 7.638 \times 10^{121}$ becomes its square root $8.739 \times 10^{60} 2\pi \times$ Planck length, which is 93.76 billion ly. The volume is 8.654×10^{184} Planck volumes ($3.491 \times 10^{182} 2\pi \times$ Planck length³), which leads to 4.423×10^{61} Planck masses ($7.041 \times 10^{60} 2\pi \times$ Planck mass) or 9.627×10^{53} kg.

This compares well to current estimates of the diameter of the observable universe of about 92.80 billion ly (error of about 1 %) and mass of 9.288×10^{53} kg (estimated range $9.102 - 9.473 \times 10^{53}$ kg, dark matter + baryonic matter). [1] The relative error for the radius is about 1 % and about 1 % (3.7 %) for mass, since the density of both objects is the same. The observable universe might be related to the direct product of the sporadic groups.

Discussion

The fact that our object has a very slightly larger volume and mass than the observable universe can be resolved via the anthropic principle. If there are many civilizations in the universe and the universe is cyclic, we should find ourselves just right in the middle of the cycle. Or it might be an indication of new physics (for example VSL theories).

It's possible that nature uses some kind of mechanism based on the sporadic groups to measure distances. For example, once an object gets to within $2\pi \times$ Planck length, it might get stabilized from all six sides by the members of the 6 pariahs. And these can travel inside a capsule created by the rest of the sporadics or by the Monster group. This mechanism might be finite, losing its ability to control the movement of our object in about 10^{122} steps.

Conclusion

It has been shown that the direct product of the 26 sporadic groups has certain correspondence with the size and mass of the universe. The significance of this correspondence is unclear.

References

1. Paul Halpern and Nick Tomasello, Size of the Observable Universe, <https://dx.doi.org/10.22606/adap.2016.13001>